

eCharge4Drivers is working on more convenient charging options for you to go electric!

eCHARGE
4DRIVERS

Easy charging, easy driving

An EU-supported Horizon 2020 project, **eCharge4Drivers** improves the Electric-Vehicle charging experience in urban areas and on interurban corridors.

HOW?

By developing and demonstrating user-friendly and innovative charging stations and solutions.

eCharge4Drivers will provide:

- Enhanced e-mobility services i.e. booking, multi-user routing, roaming, smart charging, and a charging location planning tool
- Advanced user friendly charging technologies and services with enhanced information for passengers and light vehicles, ultra-fast conductive charging stations, uni/bi-directional low power DC stations and battery swapping services
- Recommendations for standardisation, legal and regulatory frameworks
- Guidelines for investors and authorities to develop sustainable charging infrastructure and services.

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Testing, evaluating and replicating

eCharge4Drivers will be integrated in six urban areas and Trans-European road corridors in four countries, providing a range of charging experiences and meeting different charging needs.

The goal? To provide charging services that can be replicated in Europe and beyond.

URBAN AREAS

1. Barcelona, Spain
2. Grenoble, France
3. Berlin, Germany
4. Luxembourg
5. Zellik, Belgium
6. Bari, Italy

TEN-T CORRIDORS

7. Austria
8. Northern Italy
9. Greece
10. Istanbul & Western Turkey

Consortium

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